

Romania's Holistic Development in its Transition from Totalitarianism to Democracy

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ABSTRACT: This paper offers a perspective on the holistic development of Romania, a former communist society which collapsed more than a quarter century ago. The transition from a totalitarian regime to democracy in Romania was the most violent transition out of all political changes in Eastern Europe, leading to the execution of the dictatorial couple Nicolae and Elena Ceaușescu, and the sacrifice of 1166 lives (IRR). Within this *status quo*, in which the dictatorship was replaced by democracy and the centralized economy by a free capitalist economy, the holistic development of the society was still a strenuous process because there were no clear social and political patterns to follow. In this context the author refers to the development of education, the importance of innovation, technology, administration and ecology. The holistic development of society continues today in spite of being obstructed by bureaucracy, corruption and various patterns of thinking inherited from the past. The conclusion of this paper is that the holistic development of society is an ongoing challenge, paving the way toward a better society.

KEY WORDS: holistic development, communism, democracy, society

Introduction

The holistic development of the society is an important concept for any group within the society as a whole and for every community within a country. In this process of development, areas such as

education, economy, environmental friendliness, material wealth, democracy, play an important role. Unlike democratic countries, that promote a multiparty political system, and open economy, in former communist countries was promoted a totalitarian political model while the individual initiative was choked, the economy was centralized, information was censored and freedom of expression was suppressed.

The year 1989 remains in the collective memory of Eastern Europe as the year of the fall of communist regimes and the transition of these communist countries from totalitarian political systems to democratic and capitalist economic systems. The fundamental problem of the transition from communism to democracy, from centralized economy to open market economy was the lack of practical models and examples. History has recorded transition from capitalism to communism, but was very poor in relation to information on the reverse process. In this way we can explain the difficult process of transition from communism to democracy which lasted decades. To be able to talk about a modern society in this context we must first refer to the past-time of Romanian society under the communist regime, and secondly to the challenges of the transition from communism to democracy.

The Romanian Society under Communism

The Romanian psychotherapist and writer Dan Gogleză explains the emergence and development of communism in Romania as a promise that fascinates, as a falling in love, when love gets him or her “in a trance”, where emotionality feelings plays an important role.¹ Communist propaganda, according to the Marxist vision, developed a strong social emotionality trend, by suggesting personal happiness and social equality between people following the principle *from each according to ability, to each according to his needs*.

In his *Manifesto of the Communist Party*, Karl Marx presented his political ideology, his view about economic and social development that would represent the basis for a new socialist society (with no distinction between social classes), that would replace the capitalist

system represented by the bourgeoisie with another system that praises egalitarianism. Among the measures proposed by Marx, his *Manifesto* include:

1. Abolition of property in land and application of all rents of land to public purposes.
2. A heavy progressive or graduated income tax.
3. Abolition of all rights of inheritance.
4. Confiscation of the property of all emigrants and rebels.
5. Centralization of credit in the hands of the state, by means of a national bank with State capital and an exclusive monopoly.
6. Centralization of the means of communication and transport in the hands of the State.
7. Extension of factories and instruments of production owned by the State; the bringing into cultivation of waste-lands, and the improvement of the soil generally in accordance with a common plan.
8. Equal liability of all to work.
9. Establishment of industrial armies, especially for agriculture.
10. Combination of agriculture with manufacturing industries; gradual abolition of all the distinction between town and country by a more equable distribution of the populace over the country.
11. Free education for all children in public schools.
12. Abolition of children's factory labor in its present form.
13. Combination of education with industrial production, etc."²

It is important to emphasize that communist ideology is not characteristic to the Romanian society; this ideology was imposed by the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR) in the aftermath of World War II. As a political ideology, from the outside of Romania, communism was "a regime of occupation imposed by force, that has survived through force and by the exercise of terror. Communism was thus forced on people and not something accepted willingly; disavowed not admitted; rejected not supported."³ Before being a communist country, Romania was a monarchy, with a capitalist economy system. From the moment when the communists came to power, they have consistently pursued implementation of the new Marxist political direction: abolition of private property, centralization of credit in the hands of the state by means of a unique national bank, centralization of means of industrial production, transport and communication, extension of the number of factories

owned by the State, uninspired relocation of people from villages to cities, free education for all children in public schools and so on.

The development of the communist system in Romania received a local flavor after 1960 when Romania has tried to distance itself from the USSR. The peak of this distancing policy was reached in 1968 when dictator Nicolae Ceaușescu strongly condemned the Soviet invasion of Czechoslovakia.

During communism in Romania political pluralism was annihilated and political party leaders were arrested, many of whom were beaten, tortured or physically excluded. Also, the private property was dissolved, all means of individual production was taken by force and passed to the State heritage. Gradually, a new privileged class, known as nomenclature, developed; it was a class close to political leaders.

According to Grudem, out of all economic systems, communism is the most dehumanizing system ever invented by man because enslaves people, destroys human freedom of choice and the entire nation becomes a huge prison.⁴

The persecution under communism was directed toward religious and ethnic minorities; at the same time, the culture of the country has been politicized being an important weapon in the arsenal of political leaders. No doubt that communism, like any ideology, requests a price to be paid, its effect lasts for a long period of time. Norman Geisler lists some of these tragic consequences of communist leaders ideas: the fascist ideas of Hitler results in more than twelve million lives during the holocaust, the Marxist ideas of Stalin suppressed at least eighteen million lives.⁵ Freedom of expression, which is a fundamental right in any democracy has been suppressed, the strong censorship developed and watched carefully to stop sneaking any kind of anticommunist ideas or concepts in newspapers, magazines or books. As W. Grudem underlined, freedom of speech has to be protected by the government because in this way human liberty, religious speech, the ability of the individuals to decide issues for themselves, to prevent the abuse of power by the government and to enable government to be chosen by the people, are protected.⁶

Accordingly, to legitimize communism, the political leaders forged the history of Romanian people, especially the history of monarchy, negating its legacy, at the same time praising “the benefits of communism.” The songs got a profound but inexpressive patriotic language, and the National Day was changed from May 10, the day of independence of Romania (May 10, 1877) to August 23 when the Romanian army switched against Germany and allied with Soviet Union (August 23, 1944).

Communist persecution did not even spare the Romanian intellectuals, who did not agree with the new policy and therefore were not enlisted in the Communist Party. Many of them were persecuted, humiliated and arrested. An open wound, that cannot be cured even after a quarter century since the Revolution of 1989, was the existence of orphanages for disabled children who were actually true concentration camps where children were beaten, tied to the bed, let to languish in misery, uncared for and starved.

During the communist regime there was almost a “starving the population” policy, with empty stores where meat, butter, cheese, coffee and fine soaps were a true luxury available just for some privileged people. Bread was rationed according to the number of family members. The fuel as petrol and diesel were also rationalized, the drivers could buy up to 20 liters of petrol per month and motorcyclists between 5 to 10 liters, depending on their engine power.

But not only the poverty was widespread at national level. The entire population was suffering of hunger and low temperature during the long winter time because the gas pressure was very low. Electricity was frequently interrupted and TV programs, highly politicized, lasted between 4 and 5 hours. Besides all these shortcomings, there was a state of general distrust between people, the population was kept in tension, a continuous terror because of the secret police or security. The dictator Ceausescu developed the so called “systematization project of the country” aiming to destroy 8000 villages and relocate the entire population to towns and cities.⁷ To save Romanian villages from destruction, a group of journalists, photographers, architects, economists formed in Belgium the organization *Opération Villages Roumains* which encourages mayors of villages from Europe to adopt Romanian villages.⁸ Following this

purpose they wrote tens of thousands of letters to Romania which slowed the crazy plan of destruction villages.

In conclusion communism was a drama experienced by the former communist countries and their societies. The failure of communism is most evident and proved by the generalization of poverty, by trampling and violation of human rights. None of the former communist countries experienced economic development comparable to the capitalist economy of western countries.

Suggestions for Holistic Development The Difficult Road from a Communist to a Capitalist Society

Intentionally, in the first part of this article, we offer relatively a wide space for presentation of social life during communism in Romania, in order to show the difficult way from communism to democracy, from a centralized economy towards a capitalist open economy, towards a holistic development of society.

In the heyday of communism almost no one believed that this political system, which affected all social strata, will collapse one day irretrievably. The year 1989 remains in recent Romanian history as the year in which the people went out in the street, risking their life under a real rain of bullets, to change a totalitarian system with a democratic one, it remains as the year when the colossus of communism crashed. In Romania this uprising against communism was powerful and general; there were thousands of injured people and 1166 dead people.⁹ Finally on the 25th of December the dictatorial couple Nicolae and Elena Ceaușescu was shot, in other words “we (Romanians) broke up of communism just as we began, by a crime.”¹⁰

The fall of communism has left a political vacuum which was required to be filled as soon as was possible. The abrupt transition from dictatorship to democracy was a social shock, it was like the sudden transition of some prisoners sentenced to life imprisonment to total freedom. An unusual new situation for that former prisoners, living in the new context of liberty, they will have for a while “the nostalgia of prison, which offers them some security, will make them

to wander a while like Ulysses.”¹¹ The wander of Romania toward democracy lasts more than we, citizen of this country, imagined.

Communism left an unwanted legacy for Romanian population, a political deprivation, poverty, environmental degradation, a centralized economy, lack of jobs, a lot of closed factories, political external isolation and lack of information. Besides of that, we inherited from communism: bureaucracy, abuse of power, corruption, dishonesty, lack of respect of the law. The process of transition was slow, it takes a lot of work to recreate the self esteem, to restore the respect for individuals and to develop ethical behavior that included undoubtedly respect for law and for the people. Paul Johnson noticed that the changes in Romania was more a change of person than a change of political regime while the old communist nomenclature has retained political and military power, changed its name and the title of parties, regained control of newspapers, radio and television stations.¹²

Soon after the fall of communism the National Salvation Front (FSN), a new political body, assumed responsibility to pave the way for free political elections, and created the opportunity for the old traditional liberal and democratic parties to emerge. The society which lost the exercise of freedom during communism, chose during that political elections many of the former communist leaders, only a few people who were not affected by the virus of communism succeeded in politics. There it was also a tendency to determine the former communist leaders of Communist Party to step back from politics, but unsuccessfully.

The fall of communism was followed by a long period of transition marked by various reforms which aimed to transform Romanian society after the pattern of the Western European model. There was a general consensus that Romania had to turn back from communism forever and develop a new society following the Western model, to follow the way of transition from communism to capitalism and switch from the centralized state economy to an open market economy. W. Grudem says that the free market has better results than the centralized economy because it meets better the desire of the population, gives liberty to the employer to hire employees which are best suited for the job, and allows

freedom for the people to work where they fit better.¹³ According to sociologist and political researcher Vladimir Pasti, in 2004, after 15 years of efforts for Romanian people, the process of transition from communism to democracy, from centralized economy to capitalism system ended.¹⁴

An important component of the holistic development of society is the development of education. If communism focused on transmission of theoretical information and the peoples' ability to memorize this information, the holistic aspect of education involves training toward practical transformation, development of personal gifts and inclinations, in other words to help the person to develop himself. Also the formation of different kind of networks for sharing of ideas or information is an important component of holistic development, which is in opposition to individualism and competition promoted by communism.¹⁵

Finally, finding a practical framework for the application of knowledge, and not just the accumulation of theoretical knowledge, help to develop holistic society. Considering these prospects, the holistic education aims to find different ways for the development of individual identity. It is interesting to note that according to some social analysts, the social maturation has as an indicator not the intelligence but the empathy, the emotional ability of resonance to the environment. Reduction or absence of empathy is dangerous both for individuals and for the mentality of the nation.¹⁶

Holistic development of society requires recognition of the importance of innovation and the influence of technology on society, especially for the younger generation. As we know, modern technology is used today on a large scale in business and administration. The impact of technology is beneficial because it makes life easier, saves time, helps to develop business, opens opportunities for communication between students, people, politicians and society as a whole. Technology exerts a powerful mirage in this postmodern time, it permits companies to search world-wide for capital, for lower costs on products and for raw materials. But, in spite of that, we have to be cautious using technology because it can hinder the direct relationship between people, it can affect trust between employees and employer since it affects, in a way the privacy of

people, the first having the feeling of being watched during working time.¹⁷ Today, Romania is a European country with great openness for technological development, is a country where there are a large number of large companies from all over the world.

Holistic development also requires a harmonious development, a good balance between the rural and the urban areas. Unfortunately, in Romania, the rural areas where agricultural activities happen, which is a major one, didn't know as a profound development as the urban areas. A lot of means for working the land remained largely rudimentary, many irrigation systems were damaged and many young people left the village to study at universities in the cities, or to work in urban areas where salaries are higher.

Aiming the holistic development of Romanian society in its new democracy, we can't avoid talking about a high level of conscience, a clear ecological commitment and a real fight against air and water pollution. The conscience of people in society, especially of the moral conscience, according with Carl Henry is like a mudlark in contemporary life, its paternity is questioned, its existence is troublesome, its claim for attention and responsibility is burdensome.¹⁸ The duty and the imperative of this generation is to show respect for the environment, „an ethical imperative of respect not only for the right of the present generations to a healthy environment, but also the right of future generations to inherit from present generations, a healthy and ecologically balanced environment”¹⁹ The earth is rich in minerals and raw materials, according to J. Stott, God stored in this planet different resources as water, food, clothing, shelter, energy and has given to people the domination over these resourced.²⁰

Unfortunately, massive deforestation, water and air pollution are some of the challenges that the current generation must solve both for the sake of our present time and for our children's future. Exploitation of natural resources must be done in a reasonable way, not in a selfish and greedy manner, according to theologian W. Grudem, people possess ingenuity in discovering and developing new sources of energy in such a way that „the amount of energy remaining in these sources will last even beyond the current predictions.”²¹ More and more people in former communist countries develop today

a friendly attitude toward nature, they start to use more products that are environmentally friendly and to recycle materials as glass, metals and paper. People of the third Millennium have to exercise a good stewardship which involve living with an awareness that „we are managers not owners; that we are caretakers of God’s assets, which he has entrusted to us for this brief season here on earth.”²²

Conclusions

Holistic development of the Romanian society, released from the communist political regime after 45 years of oppression, represents the major challenge in the last quarter of century. Since the revolutions and riots against the communist political system during the year of 1989, the people in this Eastern European country hope for a better standard of living, for an economic development of the country following the example of Western European countries. We noticed that the transition from a totalitarian to a democratic system, which is an obligatory transition for a holistic development of society, was neither easy nor simple. Many Romanians were disappointed by political class, by the price of transition, by bureaucracy, and as a consequence they have gone to work abroad for a better-paid job and for an easier life. We are optimistic about the holistic development of the country because it is a continuous process, sometimes hindered by the scourge of corruption and lack of vision, but the holistic development continues to put its mark on society more strongly today as ever, now at the beginning of the third millennium.

NOTES

- ¹ Dan Goglează, „Preluarea trecutului comunist. O răfuială analitică cu moștenirile de mentalitate,” în *Viața cotidiană în comunism*, ed. Adrian Neculau (Iași: Polirom, 2004), 347.
- ² Cf. <https://www.marxists.org/archive/marx/works/download/pdf/Manifesto.pdf> (Last accessed: October 19, 2014)
- ³ Alexandru-Florin Platon, „Între descriere și analiză. Repere ale unei istorii sociale a vieții cotidiene în comunism,” în *Viața cotidiană în comunism*, ed. Adrian Neculau (Iași: Polirom, 2004), 31.
- ⁴ Wayne Grudem, *Politics-According to the Bible* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2010), 262.
- ⁵ Norman Geisler, *Systematic Theology*, vol. 2 (Minneapolis, MN: Bethany House, 2003), 18.
- ⁶ Grudem, *Politics-According to the Bible*, 4.
- ⁷ Paul Johnson, *O istorie a lumii moderne 1920–2000* (București: Humanitas, 2005), 735.
- ⁸ Dennis Deletant, *Istoria României* (București: Editura Enciclopedică, 1998), 565.
- ⁹ Cf. <http://www.agerpres.ro/social/2014/05/29/institutul-revolutiei-romane>, (Last accessed: November 4, 2016)
- ¹⁰ Goglează, „Preluarea trecutului...,” 366.
- ¹¹ Ibid., 359.
- ¹² Johnson, *O istorie a lumii moderne*, 736.
- ¹³ Grudem, *Politics*, 277.
- ¹⁴ Vladimir Pasti, *Noul capitalism românesc* (Iași: Polirom, 2006), 21.
- ¹⁵ Cf. <http://fizcom.blogspot.ro/2008/03/despre-o-abordare-holista-in-educatie.html> (Last accessed: November 4, 2016)
- ¹⁶ Goglează, „Preluarea trecutului...,” 365.
- ¹⁷ Scott B. Rae, Kenman L. Wong, *Beyond Integrity*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2004), 420–421.
- ¹⁸ Carl F. H. Henry, *Etica reștină personală* (Oradea: Cartea Creștină, 2004), 591.
- ¹⁹ Cf. <http://www.omicsonline.com/open-access/approaches-and-strategies-for-holistic-social-development> (Last accessed: October 18, 2016)
- ²⁰ John Stott, *Issues Facing Christians Today*, 4th ed., (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 148.
- ²¹ Grudem, *Politics*, p. 361.
- ²² Randy Alcorn, *Money Possesions and Eternity* (Carol Stream IL: Tyndale House Publishers, 2003), 152.